

**INSTRUMENTED IMPACT BEHAVIOR OF ULTEM 9085 PANELS
PRODUCED BY ADDITIVE MANUFACTURING**Thomas J. Whitney¹, Alex R. Elsbrock², and Robert L. Lowe³¹ Department of Civil and Environmental Engineering and Engineering Mechanics, University of Dayton, 300 College Park Ave., Dayton, Ohio 45469, twhitney1@udayton.edu² University of Dayton Research Institute, University of Dayton, 1700 S. Patterson Blvd., Dayton, Ohio 45409, aelsbrock1@udayton.edu³ Department of Mechanical and Aerospace Engineering, University of Dayton, 300 College Park Ave., Dayton, Ohio 45469, rlowe1@udayton.edu**Keywords:** Fused deposition modeling, Instrumented impact testing, Finite-element modeling, ULTEM 9085**ABSTRACT**

Instrumented impact testing was conducted on ULTEM 9085 panels fabricated using fused deposition modeling (FDM). Panels of various thickness, print direction, and environmental conditioning were examined. Statistically significant differences in peak load and absorbed energy were noted among the tested panels. Finite-element simulations of the impact tests were performed in LS-DYNA using an elastic-plastic constitutive model, calibrated to quasi-static tensile data. The numerical simulations showed good agreement with experimental load-displacement curves up to peak load. Our results suggest that continuum constitutive models and commercial finite-element analysis tools, calibrated to limited but physically congruent mechanical test data, show promise for first-order predictions of the pre-failure mechanical performance of as-built FDM components.

1 INTRODUCTION

Fused filament fabrication, more commonly known as fused deposition modeling (FDM), is the most popular process for additively manufacturing (3D printing) polymer components. FDM is an extrusion-based process where thermoplastic polymer filament feedstock is pulled by a pair of drive wheels into an extrusion head and subsequently heated, quasi-melted, and deposited onto a build platform. As the deposition process proceeds along a prescribed toolpath, a three-dimensional part is built up layer-by-layer through a successive process of solidification and inter-filament fusion. In recent years, attention within the FDM community has shifted toward the production of functional, load-bearing parts for various automotive, aerospace, and biomedical applications. These functional/structural applications necessitate a sound understanding of the mechanical properties of FDM materials and, in particular, the influence of FDM manufacturing *process parameters* on *mechanical properties*.

The process-property relationship in FDM materials has been the subject of numerous experimental investigations, many of which are summarized in the recent review articles of Popescu et al. [1] and Dizon et al. [2]. Process parameters of interest include extrusion temperature, layer height, raster width, raster angle and pattern, air gap, and build orientation, to name but a few. Representative mechanical properties of interest include elastic modulus, tensile strength, and elongation at fracture from tensile testing; compressive strength from compression testing; flexural strength from 3-point bend testing; and impact strength from Charpy impact testing. FDM thermoplastic materials, as a whole, tend to be weaker when compared to an injection-molded part made of the same thermoplastic. The most commonly studied thermoplastics are ABS and PLA, with substantially fewer investigations on emerging FDM thermoplastics such as ULTEM 9085 that are well-suited for structural and functional end-use components [1].

ULTEM 9085 is a high-temperature amorphous thermoplastic blend of polyetherimide (PEI) and polycarbonate (PC) which meets FAA fire, smoke, and toxicity requirements. It is used in a variety of industries and is of interest to several prominent aerospace original equipment manufacturers (OEMs). Bagsik et al. [3] investigated the impact of build orientation on the tensile and compressive properties

of FDM ULTEM 9085. Later, Bagsik and Schöppner [4] extended their previous design of experiments to include raster angle, raster width, and air gap. Motaparti et al. studied the influence of build direction, raster angle, and air gap on the compressive [5] and flexural [6] properties of FDM ULTEM 9085. Fischer and Schöppner [7] performed tensile fatigue tests on FDM ULTEM 9085 to generate S-N curves and assess lifetime for different build orientations. Zaldivar et al. [8] investigated the effect of build orientation on the tensile and thermal properties of FDM ULTEM 9085. Later, Zaldivar et al. [9] studied the impact of moisture content on the tensile properties of FDM ULTEM 9085 for different build orientations. Gebisa and Lemu investigated the role of air gap, raster width, raster angle, contour number, and contour width on the compressive [10] and flexural [11] properties of FDM ULTEM 9085. Byberg et al. [12] studied the influence of raster angle/pattern and build orientation on the tensile, compressive, and flexural properties of FDM ULTEM 9085. Ng and Brennan [13] investigated the mechanical performance of FDM ULTEM 9085 at elevated temperatures and in radioactive environments.

To the best of our knowledge, instrumented impact test data for FDM ULTEM 9085 – useful, for instance, for assessing component integrity during an automobile crash – is presently unavailable in the literature. Also, the use of commercial finite-element software for modeling FDM component-level performance and predictive simulation-aided FDM part design is limited. To the best of our knowledge, it has yet to be shown if coupon-level data taken from mechanical testing can be used to calibrate an inelastic material model in a commercial finite-element code and simulate (even to first order) the performance (deformation and failure) of a load-bearing part or component, regardless of its internal build geometry. The present paper represents a first step toward resolving this open question. If ultimately realized, a finite-element-based computational simulation tool (that can be calibrated using a relatively small set of mechanical tests) that reliably predicts the performance of load-bearing FDM parts would be a gamechanger in the FDM community.

2 EXPERIMENTS

2.1 Materials

ULTEM™ 9085 (Stratasys), a high-temperature amorphous thermoplastic blend of polyetherimide (PEI) and polycarbonate (PC), was chosen for this investigation. A FORTUS 900mc FDM 3D printer (Stratasys, Eden Prairie, MN) was used to produce all test specimens. Test specimens were manufactured in a variety of build orientations, as defined by ASTM 52921 [14]; refer to Figs. 1 and 2. Associated with each test coupon is a set of three letters (e.g., YXZ). The first letter corresponds to the direction of loading with respect to the standard XYZ build platform coordinates, the second letter indicates the transverse (in-plane) direction, and the third letter indicates the thickness (out-of-plane) direction. Test specimens were fabricated with two contours around the perimeter, $\pm 45^\circ$ rasters as the infill pattern, a -0.0015 in. raster-to-raster air gap, 0.000 in. contour-to-raster air gap, and 0.0215 in. raster width, leading to a nominal relative density of 88.5%. Stratasys Insight™ and Control Center™ software were used for controlling slicing and adjusting process parameters. Prior to mechanical testing, specimens underwent either “dry” (normal) or “wet” (saturated) environmental conditioning, with “wet” corresponding to 168 hours of exposure to an elevated-temperature/elevated-humidity environment (160 °F/95% RH) and a final moisture content of 0.7% by weight.

Figure 1: FDM machine coordinate system for (a) upward builds and (b) downward builds (from ISO/ASTM 52921 [14]).

Figure 2: Nomenclature for (a) flat, (b) edge, and (c) vertical build orientations with respect to the global machine coordinate system (from ISO/ASTM 52921 [14]).

2.2 Tension testing

Quasi-static tension testing was conducted at room temperature (72 °F) and ambient relative humidity following ASTM D638 [15] on an Instron 5500R Model 1123 screw-driven load frame equipped with wedge grips and a 5-kip load cell with traceable calibration to NIST standards. Type I specimens were printed in the YXZ (flat), YZX (edge), and ZYX (vertical) build orientations, each with a thickness of 0.130 in. All specimens were subjected to “dry” (normal) environmental conditioning post-build. All tension tests were conducted at 0.2 in/min crosshead speed (nominal strain rate of approximately 0.001 s^{-1}). For strain measurement, each specimen was instrumented with a biaxial extensometer. Figure 3 shows representative engineering stress-strain tension test data for each of the build orientations, with six tests conducted for each build.

Figure 3: Engineering stress-strain tensile test data for the (a) YXZ (flat), (b) YZX (edge), and (c) ZXY (vertical) build orientations. Specimens underwent normal post-build environmental conditioning and were tested at room temperature and humidity [16].

2.3 Instrumented impact testing

Instrumented impact testing was performed over a range of temperatures (72 °F or room temperature, 180 °F, and 275 °F) following ASTM D3763 [17] on an Instron 5500R Model 1123 screw-driven load frame. The load frame was equipped with a 5-kN load cell for force measurement and an LVDT for displacement measurement. 152-mm disk-shaped specimens were fabricated along the YXZ (flat) and YZX (edge) build orientations, with thicknesses of 0.04 in., 0.08 in., and 0.13 in. Specimens were subjected to both “dry” and “wet” environmental conditioning post-build, as described in Section 2.1. During testing, the specimens were clamped circumferentially using a custom fixture with a 76.2-mm-diameter hole machined through its center (refer to Fig. 4); the clamping assembly was mechanically tightened to prevent slippage during testing. The plunger (impactor) was a 25.4-mm-diameter stainless steel rod with a hemispherical end, centered on the clamp hole and actuated at a constant speed of 200 m/min (vertically upward); refer again to Fig. 4. Figure 5 shows an example of a test specimen post-impact.

Figure 4: Instrumented impact test setup with custom clamping fixture and hemispherical plunger assembly

During each test, load and displacement were recorded as a function of time. Load-displacement curves were subsequently constructed from the raw data, with peak load and absorbed energy (area under the load-displacement curve) being the primary response variables of interest. Six tests were conducted for each combination of build direction, specimen thickness, environmental conditioning, and testing temperature shown in Figs. 6 and 7. Figure 6 shows an increase in peak load and absorbed energy as sample thickness increases, which is expected behavior and consistent across both the YZX (edge) and YXZ (flat) build orientations. Another key takeaway is that for a given specimen thickness, the edge builds sustain higher peak loads and are better energy absorbers than the flat builds. Note that the data in Fig. 6 is for “dry-conditioned” specimens tested at room temperature. Also note that error bars represent a 95% confidence interval on the mean using Student’s T-distribution with five degrees of freedom.

Figure 5: Example of a test specimen post-impact

Figure 6: Variation in peak load and absorbed energy with increasing specimen thickness for (a) YZX (edge) and (b) YXZ (flat) builds; specimens were exposed to “dry” environmental conditioning and tested at room temperature [16]

Figure 7 illustrates the performance of 0.130-inch-thick YZX (edge-built) and YXZ (flat-built) specimens of identical thickness (0.130 in.) under different hygrothermal conditionings – “dry” (normal) or “wet” (saturated) as described in Section 2.1 – and different test temperatures (72 °F or room temperature, 180 °F, and 275 °F). As shown in Fig. 7(a), both “dry” and “wet” YZX (edge-built) samples tested at an elevated temperature of 180 °F saw a substantial and, surprisingly, congruent increase in impact performance over “dry” samples tested at room temperature. Also surprising, the impact performance of 0.130-inch-thick YXZ (flat-built) samples (shown in Fig. 7(b)) was relatively insensitive to both hygrothermal conditioning and testing temperature.

Figure 7: Peak load and absorbed energy for (a) YZX (edge) and (b) YXZ (flat) builds under different post-build environmental conditionings and testing temperatures [16]

3 MODELING AND ANALYSIS

In this section, we perform a preliminary, proof-of-concept numerical simulation of an instrumented impact test from Section 2.3 using the explicit nonlinear finite-element code LS-DYNA. Quasi-static tensile test data from Section 2.2 is used *calibrate* a basic elastic-plastic material model in the LS-DYNA material library. Thus, the instrumented impact test serves as *validation* experiment to assess the fidelity of our finite-element model.

3.1 Constitutive and failure models

The constitutive model we employ is *MAT_24 from the LS-DYNA material library. *MAT_24 characterizes the elastic portion of the deformation with isotropic linear elasticity, and the plastic portion of the deformation with rate-independent J2 (von Mises) plasticity. Both are reasonable given the

relatively weak elastic-plastic anisotropy observed in our tensile data (refer to Fig. 3) and the anticipated weak tension-compression yield asymmetry. We identified the yield point as the linear-to-nonlinear transition in the tensile data. It should be noted that selection of the yield point was qualitative, as identifying yield in FDM parts, and glassy polymers in general, is difficult. Post-yield isotropic strain hardening in MAT_24 is modelled using user-defined, tabular, effective true (logarithmic) stress-strain data. Failure is initiated by a global critical effective plastic strain at fracture; when an element satisfies this failure criterion, it is deleted (eroded). The constitutive and failure models were calibrated using the parameters shown in Table 1, obtained from the quasi-static tensile data in Fig. 8 (refer also to Section 2.2). Note that “es” denotes effective stress and “eps” denotes effective plastic strain, both converted to their true (logarithmic) measures.

Figure 8: Quasi-static tensile test data used to generate *MAT_24 inputs, engineering stress vs engineering strain [16]

Property	Value
Density (kg/mm ³) [18]	1.34E-6
Elastic Modulus (GPa)	2.76
Poisson's Ratio	0.24
Yield Stress (GPa)	0.048
Strain at Failure	0.10
eps1, es1 (GPa)	0.0, 0.049
eps2, es2 (GPa)	0.004, 0.065
eps3, es3 (GPa)	0.013, 0.078
eps4, es4 (GPa)	0.023, 0.080

Table 1: Material parameters for FDM ULTEM 9085 used in *MAT_24

3.2 Finite-element simulations

The chosen impact test configuration was the YXZ (flat) build with a thickness of 0.130 in. and “dry” environmental conditioning tested at room temperature. The YXZ specimen was selected due to the test data showing little variation in peak load and absorbed energy with test temperature or environmental conditioning (refer to Fig. 7(b)). A three-dimensional model of this test configuration was created using

the 3D CAD software SolidWorks (2019 version, Dassault Systemes, Waltham, MA). A finite-element mesh was generated using the commercial grid-generation software HyperMesh (2017 version, Altair, Troy, MI). To simplify the model, the clamping fixture was modeled as two fixed concentric rings “tied” to the circumference of the disk-shaped test specimen (see Fig. 9), accomplished using the “equivalence nodes” feature in HyperMesh. Numerical simulations were performed using the explicit nonlinear finite-element software LS-DYNA (version R10.1.0, LSTC, Livermore, CA). The specimen and fixture were discretized using 3D constant-stress 8-node solid hex (brick) elements (ELFORM = 1). The *CONTROL_HOURLASS card (with hourglass formulation IHQ = 6) was included in the LS-DYNA input deck to account for the tendency of under-integrated elements to hourglass. The model contains 145,790 nodes and 127,564 elements.

Figure 9: Instrumented impact test FEA geometry (side view)

The stainless-steel plunger/impactor was modeled using *MAT_20, a rigid material model. As discussed in Section 3.1, the ULTEM 9085 specimen was modeled using *MAT_24, an elastic-plastic material model calibrated to the experimental data in Table 1. The punch velocity was prescribed using the *BOUNDARY_PRESCRIBED_MOTION_RIGID card and the DOF option. The punch was initially offset from the surface of the test sample. Automatic surface-to-surface contact was implemented with segment-based contact (SOFT = 2 option). The simulation terminated normally in approximately 20 minutes using a shared-memory parallel version of LS-DYNA running on 8 CPUs. Figure 10 depicts a representative von Mises stress field in the specimen after impact, showing smooth contours and axisymmetric stresses. The simulated fracture morphology agrees reasonably well with the corresponding experiment (cf. Figs. 5 and 10).

Figure 10: Top and side views of test specimen showing von Mises stress field post-fracture

Force-displacement curves from the finite-element simulation were compared with instrumented impact test data; refer to Figs. 11 and 12. The raw test data exhibited substantial ringing (Fig. 11), most likely due to impact-induced waves propagating through the test article and fixture. Thus, a 10-point moving average was used to smooth the data (Fig. 12).

Figure 11: Experimental (raw data) and numerical force-displacement curves

A comparison of the numerical and experimental results before peak load reveals similar global trends and generally good agreement. However, the simulation underestimates the peak load by about 35% (170 lb. vs. 240 lb., respectively). This discrepancy is likely due to the difference in strain rates between the instrumented impact tests (about 1000 s^{-1}) and the quasi-static tensile tests (0.001 s^{-1}) used to calibrate the material model, with the quasi-static data not properly accounting for the expected “strengthening effect” at higher strain rates.

Figure 12: Experimental (smoothed) and numerical force-displacement curves

After peak load is reached, both curves exhibit a similar decrease in peak loads, driven by damage accumulation and ultimately crack initiation/propagation.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The use of quasi-static tensile test data to calibrate MAT_24, an elastic-plastic constitutive model in LS-DYNA, proved to be reasonably accurate for modeling the pre-peak-load portions of the force vs. displacement curve generated by instrumented impact testing. The numerical results and experimental data showed similar trends and generally exhibited good agreement, with the exception of the simulations underestimating peak loads by about 35%. This difference is primarily attributed to the use of quasi-static tensile test data to calibrate the material model, even though the instrumented impact test was conducted at higher strain rates; in other words, the rate-sensitivity of ULTEM 9085 was not properly accounted for. The FDM material was also assumed to be continuous and homogenous in the constitutive and finite-element models, meaning that individual raster paths, imperfections in bonding, microvoids, etc. were not modeled. MAT_24 also assumed isotropic elastic-plastic material properties and a relatively simple failure model. Thus, our results could likely be improved by calibrating our current constitutive model to tensile (and compression, shear, etc.) data at higher strain rates, more accurately modeling the mesostructure of the FDM impact test specimen, and/or jettisoning MAT_24 in favor of a more sophisticated material and failure model. Nevertheless, our results are promising and suggest that robust predictive modeling practices for quantifying the deformation and failure of functional FDM parts can be achieved.

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